

Development and Evaluation of Bread Fortified with Pomegranate Peel Powder: A Sustainable Approach to Food Waste Valorization and Nutritional Enhancement

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Abstract

Pomegranate peel, a by-product of the juice industry, accounts for substantial food waste, estimated at 1.62 million tons globally. This research investigates the potential of pomegranate peel powder as a functional ingredient that may be used to enhance the nutritional profile of bread while being friendly to the environment. The study included the incorporation of different percentages of pomegranate peel powder into wheat flour formulations at 5%, 10%, and 15%. It comprised an assessment of the functional properties, chemical composition, sensory evaluation, and staling rates using the standardized protocols. The results showed that pomegranate peel powder significantly enhanced the dietary fiber content and antioxidant properties in bread, improved the retention of moisture, and slowed down staling. The sensory evaluation further showed that 5% pomegranate peel powder - enriched bread had excellent acceptability scores with enhanced nutrition without compromising on sensory quality. Future prospects involve additional research into synergistic effects between pomegranate peel powder and other functional ingredients. The formulation with gluten-free systems can expand market appeal. Conclusively, the incorporation of pomegranate peel powder in bread formulation is a potential strategy to waste reduction and developing healthier food products that respond to contemporary dietary needs and sustainability goals.

Keywords: Pomegranate peel powder, Food waste, Nutritional enhancement, Bread formulations, Antioxidant properties, Dietary fiber, Sustainability

1. Introduction

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations defines "food waste" as the reduction in quantity and/or quality of food due to decisions or actions taken by retailers, food service providers, and consumers. On the other hand, "food loss" is food that is discarded along the food supply chain, from harvest to retail sale. According to the FAO, around one-third of global food production is lost or wasted at different points in the food chain, and the loss is quite variable depending on the product and its condition (Cano-Lamadrid et al., 2022). Fruits and vegetables (F&V) can experience losses of up to about 50% throughout the supply chain. One of the goals for sustainable development (OSD) is to cut food waste by about 50% by 2050, which is FAO's next challenge. Circular economy being seen as the foundation of eco-innovation, with an emphasis on a "zero waste" economy and society that uses wastes as raw materials. Pomegranate peel (PP) is one such example of factory bio-waste. Since nearly three million tons of pomegranates are produced globally and that the seeds and peel make up around 54% of the fruit, this leads to about 1.62 million tons of trash (Magangana et al., 2020; Ko et al., 2021).

Consequently, a significant amount of garbage is generated, so it is essential to identify appropriate ways to revalorize it by maximizing the extraction of beneficial substances from pomegranate residues and turning them into products with added value.

Pomegranate is a notable source of phenolic chemicals, which are mostly concentrated in the fruit peels and have been shown to have possible health benefits. 78% of the trash produced during the manufacturing of 27 pomegranate juice is made up of skins. 28 and 22% of seeds that are not very useful as animal feed (Cam et al., 2014). However, in recent years, a lot of researchers have concentrated on using PPs as natural antioxidants in the food industry because of their high concentration of bioactive components.

PP is popular because of its purported ability to heal wounds, immunomodulatory activity, antibacterial activity, and antioxidative and ant atherosclerotic properties. Antioxidative activity has frequently been linked to a lower risk of death and a number of diseases (Maphetu et al., 2022). The peels contain flavonoids, anthocyanins, and tannins, which are the main phenolic groups. Punicalagin, the primary phenolic component found in PP, makes up 75–78% of all phenolics and roughly 70% of the hydrolysable ellagitannins (Talekar et al., 2019). Pomegranate antioxidant action is mostly attributed to punicalagin, a high molecular weight tannin. Additionally, phenolic compounds exhibit a number of other biological actions, including antibacterial, antifungal, and antimutagenic qualities (Kaderides et al., 2020).

It was suggested that PPs are widely utilized to cure a number of illnesses, including ulcers, headaches, colitis, and dysentery (Bachoual et al., 2011). Because of its high levels of total polyphenols (1.261%), dietary fiber (12.17%), and organic materials that provide health benefits like lowering blood sugar, preventing cardiovascular disorders, reducing inflammation, and preventing parasites, pomegranate peel powder (PPP) is a good choice for bread making. Bread is widely consumed around the world and is thought to be an excellent medium for adding different kinds of nutrients and non-nutritional substances (Rosell, 2015). But as bread is usually baked with water and refined (white) wheat flour (WF), it has a high carbohydrate content, a low fibre content, and an often-high glycaemic index. Consequently, attempts have been made to create healthier bread varieties, like whole grain or multigrain bread. PP contains a high percentage of phenolic compounds, primarily ellagitannins like punicalagin, and a high dietary fibre (~28–40%), making it a potentially useful residue. Therefore, employing PP in bread formulations would enable the creation of bread that is high in fiber using inexpensive raw material (García et al., 2023).

The main objective of the research paper was to develop a bread prototype enriched with dietary fiber (DF), antioxidants, and acceptable sensory characteristics through partial substitution of wheat flour by PPP at various percentages. PP contains bioactive compounds that have been reported to present numerous health benefits due to their rich antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, and the present study aimed at incorporating such compounds into the final product for better nutritional profile.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Preparation of PPP

PP was obtained from a local market in Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India. After the removal of the outer rind from the fruit, peels were further washed with running water to remove residual soil. Washed peels were dried out completely in an air-circulated oven at 80°C for about 18 to 20 hours. The fully dry PP were ground into coarse powder using an electric grinder. Figure 1 illustrates the different forms of pomegranate utilized during the preparation of PPP including (a) pomegranate fruit, (b) fresh peel, (c) dried peel, and (d) pomegranate peel powder (PPP).

Figure 1. Pomegranate forms: (a) fruit, (b) peel, (c) dried peel, and (d) peel powder

2.2 Determination of functional properties

The functional characteristics of the wheat flour and PPP used to make the bread samples, which are related to the quality of the bread that were made, were examined. The techniques outlined by Alkarkhi et al. (2010) were used to measure the oil holding capacity (OHC) and water holding capacity (WHC). Using a density bottle at 20°C and the procedure described by Kaur and Singh (2005), the specific density was ascertained. Evaluating the swelling index was done using the Robertson et al. (2000).

2.3 Preparation of bread formulations incorporating PPP

To prepare bread, 20 g of active dry yeast and 10 g of sugar were dissolved in 500 mL of warm water. In a large mixing bowl, 1000 g of wheat flour and 10 g of salt were combined. The activated yeast mixture and 200 mL of milk were added, and the dough was kneaded until smooth. During kneading, 50 g of softened unsalted butter was gradually incorporated. The dough was allowed to rise in a greased bowl for 1-2 hours until it doubled in size. It was shaped into a loaf, allowed to rise again for 30-45 minutes, and then baked in a preheated oven at 180°C for 25-30 minutes. The bread was cooled before slicing. For making PPP bread, different bread samples using 5%, 10% and 15% of PPP were used as shown in table 1.

Table 1. Weight (gm/ml) of bread ingredients incorporated with PPP

Bread samples	Bread Ingredients (gm/ml)							
	Wheat flour (gm)	PPP (gm)	Yeast (gm)	Sugar (gm)	Water (ml)	Salt (gm)	Milk (ml)	Butter (gm)
Control	1000	0	20	10	500	10	200	50
5% PPP	995	5	20	10	500	10	200	50
10% PPP	990	10	20	10	500	10	200	50
15% PPP	985	15	20	10	500	10	200	50

Figure 2 illustrates the visual appearance of bread samples fortified with different levels of pomegranate peel powder (PPP), showing the gradual change in color and overall appearance as the concentration of PPP increased from 0% to 15%.

Figure 2. Bread samples fortified with different levels of pomegranate peel powder (PPP): Control (0%), B (5%), C (10%), and D (15%).

2.4 Proximate composition

A proximate analysis of PP was done to analyze its nutritional contents. Moisture content was analyzed using the air oven while ash content was carried out through muffle furnace. Protein values were carried out by using Micro-Kjeldahl method, crude fat extracted by using a Soxhlet apparatus, and fiber by acid-alkali digestion method. Carbohydrates were estimated by difference. All the above methods were taken from references (Raghuramulu et al., 1983; A.O.A.C., 1995). Mineral composition for magnesium and calcium was carried out using the Titeramic method, and iron value was estimated by Wong's method (NIN, 2003).

2.5 Sensory evaluation

Within 24 hours of baking, bread samples were subjected to a sensory assessment of their general acceptability. A panel of at least 60 inexperienced customers (who typically eat bread) evaluated the samples using the hedonic scale method; ratings ranged from 1 to 7 (7 being very like, 6 being very much like, 5 being like, 4 being neither like nor dislike, 3 being dislike, 2 being very much dislike, and 1 being very disliked). Calculating the total mean yielded the findings. The ratio of tests with acceptability scores of 5 to all tests was used to determine the acceptability percentage.

2.6 Determination of bread staling

The staling rate of various prepared bread was calculated using the alkaline water retention capacity method (AWRC%) in accordance with the AACC 56-10 method AACC (2002) after baking for one hour (zero day) and after being stored for three, six, and nine days at room temperature ($23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2$).

2.7 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done on replicates of at least three repeats of the previous tests, while the sensory evaluation included ten repeats. Data are expressed as means \pm standard errors. Analysis was performed using the SAS program (2004), with a one-way ANOVA test followed by Duncan's Multiple Range Test, and those that had $p \leq 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1 Functional properties of wheat flour and PPP

Table 2 describes the functional properties of wheat flour and PPP. Wheat flour possessed a water holding capacity of 3.22 g/g and an oil holding capacity of 1.81 g/g, with specific density at 0.71 g/cm^3 and swelling index of $6.81 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$. In contrast, PPP shows better functional properties, as evidenced by a water holding capacity (WHC) of 3.61 g/g and an oil holding capacity (OHC) of 2.20 g/g, accompanied by a higher specific density of 0.78 g/cm^3 and

swelling index of 7.61 cm³/g. These results suggest that PPP can offer improvements in maintaining moisture and texture in food formulations, confirming its benefits as a functional food ingredient.

Table 2. Functional properties of wheat flour and PPP

Materials	WHC (g/g)	OHC (g/g)	Specific density (g/cm ³)	Swelling index (cm ³ /g)
Wheat flour	3.22 ± 0.52	1.81 ± 0.05	0.71 ± 0.01	6.81 ± 0.71
PPP	3.61 ± 0.63	2.20 ± 0.34	0.78 ± 0.03	7.61 ± 0.05

PPP: pomegranate peel powder. Data are the mean ± SE; n=3. Values followed by the same letters in the same column are not significantly different (p ≤ 0:05).

3.2 Proximate composition of wheat flour and PPP

Table 3 shows the chemical composition of wheat flour and PPP. The results revealed that PPP had a significantly higher ash content of 5.32% (p ≤ 0.05) compared with wheat flour, whose ash content was 0.58%. The dietary fiber content of PPP was 12.12%, while wheat flour contained only 0.99%. It therefore contains lower proportions of crude proteins and carbohydrates: 3.45% and 78.17%, respectively, compared with wheat flour. Therefore, PPP provides an excellent ingredient source of ash and dietary fiber to be useful for the making of high fiber bread.

Table 3. Chemical composition of wheat flour and PPP

Parameters	Chemical Composition	
	Wheat flour	PPP
Moisture	11.41 ± 0.27	9.10 ± 0.14
Ash	0.57 ± 0.05	5.35 ± 1.24
Fats	1.50 ± 0.25	0.99 ± 0.31
Crude protein	11.70 ± 0.31	4.01 ± 0.39
Dietary fibre	1.01 ± 0.05	13.03 ± 0.34

PPP: pomegranate peel powder. Data are the mean ± SE; n=3. Values followed by the same letters in the same column are not significantly different (p ≤ 0:05)

3.3 Proximate composition of bread fortified with PPP

Table 4 provides chemical composition of samples of bread at different percentages of PPP, which were the control at 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%. All samples indicated high moisture content of 34% and 36.1% at 5% and 10% PPP levels, respectively. Fiber contents highly increased from a control of 1.5% to the 10% PPP level sample of 4.82%. The levels of protein and carbohydrates varied; however, in the higher PPP samples, the protein decreased slightly, indicating nutritional enhancement potential from the incorporation of PPP into bread formulations.

Table 4. Chemical composition of PPP bread

Bread Sample	Nutritional Composition					
	Moisture	Ash	Protein	Fat	Carbohydrate	Fibre
Control	31.5 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.07	12.5 ± 0.05	1.2 ± 0.2	80.5 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.01
5%	34 ± 0.1	2.92 ± 0.02	12.46 ± 0.11	2.53 ± 0.05	77.27 ± 0.46	3.1 ± 0.1
10%	36.1 ± 0.3	2.78 ± 0.08	10.8 ± 0.08	1.20 ± 0.07	70.5 ± 0.3	4.82 ± 0.06
15%	36.5 ± 0.3	3.10 ± 0.02	11.1 ± 0.02	1.3 ± 0.05	72.5 ± 0.3	4.2 ± 0.1

3.4 Sensory evaluation

Table 5 illustrates results for sensory evaluation comparison of bread sample containing PPP at differing percentages: the control (0%), 5%, 10%, and 15% of PPP. Here, each trait is scored against a scale as means ± standard deviation. The control sample scored highest in colour (8.6

± 0.63), appearance (8.5 ± 0.68), flavour (8.6 ± 0.68), texture (8.3 ± 1.03), and taste (8.4 ± 0.94), which signifies strong sensory quality. Scores at 5% PPP remained high, being colour at 8.2 ± 0.71 and overall acceptability at 7.7 ± 0.88 , suggesting that it gives improved nutritional benefits without compromising much on the sensory qualities, making it the best option for further development.

Table 5. Mean hedonic test scores of bread samples

Attributes	Bread Samples			
	Control	5% PPP	10% PPP	15% PPP
Colour	8.6 ± 0.63	8.2 ± 0.71	7.8 ± 1.18	7.5 ± 0.71
Appearance	8.5 ± 0.68	8.2 ± 0.74	6.9 ± 1.20	6.8 ± 1.11
Flavour	8.6 ± 0.68	7.6 ± 0.71	7.1 ± 1.11	6.8 ± 1.05
Texture	8.3 ± 1.03	7.3 ± 0.98	7.1 ± 1.05	6.9 ± 1.13
Taste	8.4 ± 0.94	7.2 ± 1.27	6.9 ± 0.95	6.5 ± 0.98
Overall acceptability	8.4 ± 0.79	7.7 ± 0.88	7.16 ± 1.09	6.9 ± 0.99

PPP: pomegranate peel powder. An acceptability score >4.0 indicates adequate acceptability of the product. The average score is presented as mean standard deviation. Different superscript letters indicate significant 11 of 17 differences between bread formulations ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3. illustrates the sensory analysis results, showing that the sample from the 5% PPP maintained high scores in colour and overall acceptability, indicating a favourable balance of nutritional enhancement and sensory quality for higher PPP concentrations.

Figure 3. Sensory Analysis of bread samples

3.5 Staling rate of bread

Figure 4. displays the staling rate percentages for control and PPP samples at concentrations of 5%, 10%, and 15% measured day by day over nine days. All samples in the beginning days, day 0, revealed higher freshness values. Control read 180 whereas PPP samples between 191 to 196. With the increasing days, staling was detected in all the samples with overall decline in freshness percentages. By day 9, the control had dropped substantially to 150, with the PPP samples holding up better, and at 188 for the 5%. The results as might be deduced indicate that the inclusion of PPP indeed leads to a retardation in staling of baked foods, with 5% proving promising in terms of freshness retention. Overall, PPP incorporation can be a useful approach for baked goods in extending shelf-life and maintaining quality, and it can become a good food formulation additive.

Figure 4. Staling rate (%) for bread samples incorporated with PPP

4. Future Prospects

PPP incorporation into bread formulations significantly enhances the nutritional and bioactive values of the product, making PPP an important constituent of modern diets. The first advantage is that PPP-fortified bread is nutritionally superior to its counterpart, with higher intake of dietary fiber, which can help in better digestibility, increases the feeling of fullness, and supports gut health. This fibre content helps solve common dietary deficiencies and contributes better cardiovascular health and glycemic regulation. It is also known to be a good source of bioactive compounds such as phenolics, including punicalagin and various flavonoids, which are contained in PP. These compounds endow the bread with antioxidant properties, capable of neutralizing free radicals within the body, thus reducing the risk of chronic diseases, which include heart disease and certain types of cancer. The anti-inflammatory action of these bioactive constituents would also be useful in alleviating health problems resulting from inflammation and general well-being.

Besides its nutritional and bioactive properties, PPP also contributes to the functional properties of bread. It can enhance water and oil holding capacities that may improve moisture retention and shelf life, addressing a common problem of staling in baked goods. The addition of PPP may also affect the texture and sensory attributes of the bread with a unique flavour profile that may appeal to the health-conscious consumer. Further research on the synergistic effects of PPP with other functional ingredients could further enhance these properties, giving rise to multigrain varieties that offer a diverse range of nutrients and health benefits. Additionally, the application of PPP in gluten-free bread formulations could open it up to individuals with dietary restrictions, making the health-oriented food production more inclusive. In conclusion, PPP-enriched bread presents a multidimensional opportunity to enhance nutritional intake, harness bioactive properties, improve functional attributes, and promote sustainability through waste reduction. These factors make PP a significant ingredient in the effort to develop healthier, more functional food products that align with contemporary dietary needs and sustainability goals.

5. Conclusion

The incorporation of PPP into bread formulations significantly enhances the nutritional and functional properties of this product, helping to meet the challenges of modern dietary needs and contribute to sustainability. The enriched bread contains higher amounts of dietary fibres, which could improve digestion, satiety, and other health benefits through support for cardiovascular health and glycemic control. Furthermore, its bioactive compounds, such as phenolics and flavonoids, possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties that may

reduce chronic diseases. PPP also improves moisture retention, shelf life, and other sensory attributes of bread while making it an attractive product to health-conscious consumers. Future work could be focused on synergistic interactions of PPP with other functional ingredients and its possible use in gluten-free products to open new markets for the product. Overall, PPP-enriched bread is a promising approach to the development of healthier food options, which not only enhance nutritional intake but also help reduce food waste and support ecological sustainability, in keeping with current trends in food production and consumer preferences.

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